

TRANSITION TO EMPLOYMENT: INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES OF SPECIAL EDUCATION TEACHERS FOR STUDENTS WITH HEARING IMPAIRMENT

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ABSTRACT

There is an increase in the population of people with disabilities which emphasises issues concerning their inclusion in essential societal functions. For example, in the Philippines, these issues manifest in a low participation rate in jobs and the preparedness of students to transition from school to employment. Special education (SPED) teachers prepare these individuals to transition to employment through meaningful instructional strategies. The study aimed to determine the instructional strategies employed by SPED teachers to equip students with hearing impairment to transition to employment. Using a single case study design, accounts of SPED teachers of students with hearing impairment in a postsecondary educational institution in the Philippines were collected. Data collected through key informant interviews and observations revealed that the instructional strategies of SPED teachers include the use of visual aids and immersion of the students with sign language and assessments as supporting strategies. The instructional strategies of the SPED teachers target necessary skills for employment, such as communication skills, perseverance, and discipline as soft skills and business administration and computer technology as hard skills. Experiences of teachers, which revolve around employment together towards shared goals, influence the instructional strategies of teachers. Moreover, these experiences, especially the negative reality of the employment of students with hearing impairment, also shape the pedagogical decisions of teachers in using effective instructional strategies.

Keywords: Hearing impairment, instructional strategies, special education, transition to employment

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INTRODUCTION

A report documented the population of people with disabilities at over one billion people, or 16% of the world's population (World Health Organization, 2021). The large population of people with disabilities has highlighted the population's degree of inclusion and participation in normal societal functions. In support of the inclusion of people with disabilities within mainstream society, several laws and policies have been created and implemented. Among these is the Salamanca Statement and Framework for Action, which promotes and defends the inclusion and participation of the said group in one of the functions of society, education (United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization, 1994)

In the Philippine context, the Republic Act 7277, or the Magna Carta for Disabled Persons, and the Education Act of 1982, or Batas Pambansa Bilang 232, are prominent laws that protect the inclusion of Filipinos with disabilities in various societal activities, such in education and employment (*Republic Act 7277*, 1992; *Batas Pambansa BLG. 232*, 1982). In a recent development of laws for SPED and inclusive education in the country, a law mandating that all public and private schools in the country grant admission to learners with disabilities and guarantee their equal access to quality education was institutionalised through the Republic Act 11650 otherwise known as Instituting a Policy of Inclusion and Services for Learners with Disabilities in Support of Inclusive Education Act (*Republic Act No. 11650*, 2022).

The stipulated laws and policies serve as a clear basis for special education (SPED)—an educational program involving individualised teaching tools, techniques, and strategies to address and respond to the academic needs of students with disabilities or those with additional needs (Barik, n.d.). Included in the spectrum that should receive SPED programs and services are children with hearing impairment (HI). HI, as defined by World Health Organization (2021), limits a person's ability to hear and communicate when skills and assistive technologies are not sufficiently provided.

A person diagnosed with HI should be assisted with suitable accommodations and modifications to avoid negative impacts on the individual's education, employment, and intrapersonal relationships. However, lack of awareness and communication impediments are the most affecting issues in the employment of people experiencing HI (Gupta et al., 2022). Inclusivity and equity are also yet to be found in a workplace and are supported by the high percentage of reports by people with HI (Bonaccio et al., 2020). It was shown from the literature that most employed individuals with HI were not given equal opportunities and did not feel included and genuinely supported in their environment (Armstrong, 2021). The education system has also been a contributing factor for learners with HI's low participation in jobs from the irregularity of schemes and unclear and indirect career focus, causing the problem for unemployed individuals with HI (Yusof et al., 2012).

Despite numerous studies, such as those of Yusof et al. (2012) and Calimpusan and Cruz (2018), placing the education of individuals with HI in terms of transition to employment as a contributing factor to their low participation rate in employment, there are limited studies that look at this matter on a more specific lens, specifically on the instructional strategies employed by the SPED teachers. This study aims to fill in this gap and identify the instructional strategies employed by SPED teachers to transition to the employment of students with HI. More specifically, it also asks what skills these instructional strategies target and how the teaching experiences of SPED teachers impact their pedagogical decisions on the instructional strategies used to support the transition to the employment of the students.

Through a qualitative single-case design, this study sought to understand how students with HI are prepared for employment through the instructional strategies of SPED teachers. Lessons learned, and articulations from this case study provide an understanding for practitioners, curricularists, and administrators on the HI's inclusion in society, not only in the school communities but even as they transition to work.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Hearing Loss

Hearing loss can affect one or both ears, and be minor, severe, or profound, making it challenging to hear conversational discourse or loud noises (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2022). Lemke and Scherpriet (2015) stated that hearing impairment limits a person's capacity to hear and speak when relevant abilities and assistive technologies are lacking. To minimise consequences on the person's education, employment, and interpersonal relationships, a person with hearing loss should be assisted in making the appropriate changes and adaptations (WHO, 2021).

In 2019, an estimated 157 billion individuals worldwide experienced hearing loss, equivalent to one out of every five persons (WHO, 2023). The Western Pacific area has the most people with moderate-to-complete hearing loss, and nations with poor healthcare access and the quality index have higher rates of years lived with disability (Global Burden of Disease 2019 Collaborators, 2021). The total prevalence of moderate to severe people with HI in the Philippine population is 15%, 7.5% in children, 14.7% in people aged 18 to 65, and 49.1% in individuals aged 65 and above (Newall et al., 2020).

WHO (2021) states that unaddressed hearing problems (HI) significantly impact individuals' lives, especially in countries with no proper implementation of SPED. Additionally, adults with hearing loss or hard of hearing tend to have difficulty being employed due to barriers such as low-educational attainment (Dammeyer & Marschark, 2016) and lack of deaf awareness (WHO, 2023), which leads to rejection due to the inability to communicate verbally to other people. A study from Scotland found that the social status of a student with HI matters, wherein if they have a poorer background, they lower the chances of having an insecure job (Fordyce & Riddell, 2015). In the Philippines, the educational support for individuals with HI is inadequate in tertiary programs, and the emphasis of the transition program is unmanageable (Calimpusan & Cruz, 2018). Awareness of people to the deaf culture is also insufficient, which affects their psychological aspect, which causes their environmental vulnerability (Sintos, 2020).

For example, sign language is the medium of communication in the context of HIs. The Republic Act 11106 (2018) mandates using Filipino Sign Language (FSL) as the national sign language of Filipinos with HI. However, the study by Krause and Murray (2019) found that using Sign Exact English (SEE) involves American Sign Language (ASL) signs, invented signs, and signed representations of English affixes that were also mandated to be utilised in the Philippines, especially in the reading activity. This caters to the social dimension, which is a part of the HIs extrinsic motivation to establish learning continuously. Teachers' role in decision-making on how they will cater to students with HI is significant in implementing schemes for adult learners (Alasim, 2018).

With the continuance of handling students with HI, experiences arise when an institution provides mentoring to assist SPED teachers during the first year of teaching (Salleh & Tan, 2013). People associate knowing American Sign Language (ASL) as a language of communication crucial for learners with HI (Mann, 2016). It was prevalent that communication policies are vital to sustaining an efficient school wherein administrators may help instructors overcome the communication hurdles of educators to prevent and minimize issues for the teachers (Agbofa, 2022). Potter (2021) found that SPED teachers experienced the same problem and difficulties. However, they are responsible for the necessary abilities in their employment with patience and dedication to hone their ability to instruct students with HI by guiding them (Denton, 2018). Collaboration with parents is also integral for SPED teachers' experiences in making and establishing the IEP procedure, including meetings and monitoring with the involvement of a multidisciplinary team (McLeskey, 2017; McDermott, 2013; Paccaud et al., 2021).

Instructional Strategies for Learners with HI

There are different factors affecting the academic success of the students. One of the vital factors is the instructional strategies utilized by the teachers that are mostly dependent on the academic goals, the present level of performance of the students, and the different learning styles of the students irrespective of their disabilities (Thomas & Green, 2015). It is notable that for the instructional strategies to be effective and enhance the learning of the students, the teachers should be trained and flexible to the different kinds of strategies to cater to the different needs of their students (Mahmood, 2021).

Transition to Employment

Among the instructional strategies crucial in the curriculum for learners with HI is on their transition to the world of work. Universities prepare students for the short-term and long-term transition of students with HI from tertiary education to employment. According to Myers and Takayama (2019), these preparations positively affect the employment outcome of the deaf and hard of hearing. A study in 2016 by Alkahtani discusses that transition services face challenges and barriers. Some points identified are lack of government support and involvement of private sectors, and coordination of school, family, and community. In the Philippines, factors and implications in transitioning learners with HI into the workplace include negative stereotypes, added business value, added cost, and efforts at management, and social cost factors. The attitude of employers in hiring employees with HI also differs according to the position or job applying for. Applicants who are with HI are usually offered nonprofessional and blue-collar jobs – the less desirable ones (Buyayao et al., 2014). These can be attributed to the qualifications industries are looking for from their applicants.

In the Philippine context, the skills employers look for in PWDs including those who are with hearing impairment are: (1) soft human skills that strengthen team employment in the workplace, (2) problem-solving skills that help the company thrive, (3) communication skills, (4) decision-making skills, and (5) a certain level of educational attainment (Alson et al., 2019). The skills the employers look for differs depending on which industry the person will apply in. In the private sector, what most employers require to those people with hearing impairment are technical and vocational skills partnered with personal qualities and interpersonal skills (Bakar et al., 2013). The different required skills and the inadequate knowledge of the employers about the proper accommodation and strategies to help the people with hearing impairment in the workplace affect the poor employment rate of the people with hearing impairment (Doolabh & Khan, 2020).

METHODOLOGY

This study was pursued through a single case analysis as popularised by Yin (2017). The design is used in exploring lessons learned from a specific phenomenon. Articulations gathered from the cases help in improving professional practices. The researchers used a single case study to dwell into the comprehensive view within the participant's context (Gustaffson, 2017) and to have profound internal validity for assessing the correlation between interventions and outcomes (Lobo et al., 2017). In order to acknowledge the goals of the research, the researchers used purposive sampling techniques and specifically went to the community as they fit the profile required for the study to provide the "most likely yielded and useful information" (Campbell et al., 2020). The participants of this study include four (4) SPED teachers teaching students with hearing impairment in a private postsecondary institution in the Philippines.

The researchers utilized an interview protocol that was checked by a validator for the accuracy and appropriateness of the questions that were asked in the semi-structured interview. To request permission for the research to be conducted, the researchers created and sent a letter of approval addressed to the respondents stating the purpose, duration, and description of the study, including its confidentiality. The interview and observation were bound to anonymity and confidentiality following the consent form that was answered by the participants as well as the written affidavit that the sign language interpreters signed

The researchers conducted a series of trustworthiness procedures to establish trust and diminish suspicions with other researchers, which is curated by the study of Lincoln and Guba (1986). To pursue credibility, the researchers conducted member checking, administration of audit trail to confirm the findings with the raw data, a thick description for the paper that supports the reader's aligned understanding, and peer debriefing was also conducted to process and organize the researcher's understanding on the gathered data from the different respondents and lastly, to build enough trust and credibility, the researchers performed an external audit trail and sought professional help to authenticate and validate the correlation of the data gathered. The data gathered through key informant interviews was also confirmed through observation. For systematic conduct of observation, features suggested by Cohen et al. (2007) were integrated.

A thematic content analysis was applied by identifying codes, categories, and themes based on the participants' answers (Saldaña, 2012) from the one-on-one interview and classroom observation. Two (2) certified interpreters guided the analysis of the data. Precoding was first done in which the researchers familiarised the data and dissected sections of the data they had gathered using codes to label. Axial coding was also used, establishing the link

between existing codes and creating new codes, categories, and subcategories. Additionally, substantive coding is used to conceptualise codes, categories, and themes significant for the study. The iterative coding process helped the authors generate the lessons learned from this single case study.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Using thematic data analysis, this qualitative paper analysed interview transcripts and observation records on the instructional strategies employed by SPED teachers for the transition to the employment of students with HI, the skills targeted by these strategies, as well as the influence of teaching experiences on the pedagogical decisions of teachers on what strategies to use. See Figure 1.

Instructional Strategies

Figure 1: The instructional strategies employed by SPED teachers for the transition to the employment of the students with HI

The participants stated that one of the instructional strategies they utilize for the transition to the employment of students with hearing impairment is visual aids. There are four specific visual aids used, and these are (1) Videos, (2) Pictures, (3) Templates, and (4) slide presentations, which are primarily pre-downloaded from the internet. According to the participants, the usage of visual aids is important when teaching students with hearing impairment and is evident in the following statement:

P4: We do not use without PowerPoint. You cannot just say “this is..” With the deaf learners, you should have visual presentation. You cannot teach them without visuals as it will be difficult for them to process the information heard. They are not like the hearing students. Once you hear the instructions, you are good to go. With the deaf, you must have a visual presentation.

The second instructional strategy stated by the participants in the provision of different immersions, such as hands-on experiences, employment workshops, field trips, and various exposure opportunities to better gear their students for employment. The students begin their on-the-job training during their second year of college. They are also exposed to different business environments for the students to interact more with additional employees, which can help develop their understanding and knowledge about workplace situations and environments.

The participants use Sign Language as the primary mode of communication and also stated that they utilise the three (3) kinds of sign language such as American Sign Language (ASL), Sign Exact Language (SEE), and at times, Filipino Sign Language (FSL) depending on the setting.

According to the participant, students will be more prepared for the workforce once they graduate if they regularly practice practical writing that includes writing letters and documents for employment (resumes, applications, and other formal written documents).

Target Skills

Figure 2: *The target skills of teachers of students with HI necessary for the transition to employment*

The participants discussed two categories in terms of their target skills in employing their instructional strategies, such as (a) soft skills and (b) hard skills.

In the transition to the employment of students with HI, the teachers target necessary soft skills in their instructional strategies. Participants stated that their target skills in their instruction include student communication skills, including interpersonal and intrapersonal communication, discipline, and perseverance:

P3: *"[...] they share feelings [...] like experience [...], but I can't force them to open up feelings."*

P4: *"[...] we have personality development seminars every year because we have to tell them that the hearing world is different from the Deaf [...] Deaf has their own culture, their language, their tradition, their behavior is different from the hearing world." P3: "I try the best discipline [...] It's like fundamental [...] never say "sayang" no. [should be] best."*

P4: *"I try to encourage them to think about more goals, and then they will feel enlightened."*

Aside from soft skills, teachers also target the hard skills of students in their instruction. According to the participants, the hard skills they target include business administration and computer technology skills:

P3: *"[...] immediate with deaf [...] how to good know study with bachelors in science in business administration so that in future themselves they know future employment. So that they learn here four years... Now they OJT"*

P1: *"One example, how about studying computer. Example, outside I try to employment and use excel. For accounting through money and cash how to deposit. Kunyare sa IT, maexperience mo and then ituturo mo din sa class [...] para hindi ka matatakot na gawin kaya tinatry ko na turuan sila ng excel. Wag natin sila hayaan na walang matutunan."*

The participants of the study target skills for their students and consciously employ their instructional strategies aiming at these specific soft and hard skills for their student's transition to employment.

Working Together Towards Shared Goals

Figure 3: The experience of the SPED teachers influencing their instructional strategies used for the transition class to the employment of students with HI

Figure 3 illustrates the employment in progress for SPED teachers of students with HI to employment together towards shared goals. Findings have come up that Learning inside and outside the country; Teacher, Student, and Parent Collaboration; and Helping students be free of discrimination by being smart and capable influenced the SPED Teachers' experiences to employ the necessary instructional strategies for students with HI.

Learning Inside and Outside the Country

SPED Teachers for HI gained experiences based on the influence of their environment that led them in the pursuit of teaching, and adapting their experiences has enabled the participants to develop the interpersonal skills that influenced them to lead and guide the students for the students. All of the participants' experiences were different to, put into strategy what they learned from community to school.

P2: "My experience in the organisation [NGO]. They influence me to lead, so I influence [students]; why? Example. Those experiences all [have] different [differences]. That's why my experience put the same in school; why?" [...] "Same adjust [in the environment]. In the NGO community different. In school different. Depend on perspective in community."

Moreover, according to the participants, Western and Eastern countries have more experience teaching students with HI than the Philippines, which needs more education support. This gave participants sufficient knowledge to practice skills and strategies that can be used in the country.

P4: "What I learned from other countries, for example, from America or from Europe, I try to learn, and here in the Philippines wala kasi masyadong skilled. Talagang mas skilled yung mga nasa America or sa ibang bansa like Japan or Korea." [...] "I brought it here to teach my students. Kasi here in the Philippines, limited ang education."

Parent, Student, and Teacher Collaboration

The relationship between the teacher and the student contributes a huge factor since the teacher serves as the mediator to negotiate with the parents regarding the student with HI's strengths, needs, and progress. It was mentioned that parents might not understand their child, therefore, explaining was said to be acquired that letting the teachers have an experience by influencing how they teach was vital.

P4. Relationships and connections are very instrumental to the deaf students. You also serve as mediator to their families. Their families cannot understand them. You have to explain for them. That activity, outside the classroom, influences how we teach. It is very instrumental.

To fully achieve this, they conduct regular parent-teacher conferences aside from having a one-on-one consultation with the student.

P4: *"We have regular parent-teacher conferences. So dalawa — classroom and family."*

Helping the Students Be Free of Discrimination By Being Smart and Capable

Prejudice and discrimination, according to the participants, are one of the foreseen challenges of students with HI. By identifying this issue, they are being taught to have an awareness and knowledge to be intelligent in decision-making and impose ideas to achieve what an employee should attain due to the satisfactory result that they possibly adhere to. That leads them to better involve themselves with other people despite their condition.

P4: They will be discriminated, that is why they need to be smart. Once they are employed, their bosses will value them. Well, before, the deaf community were degraded and now there is discrimination.

Negative Realities of Employment for Individuals with HI

Figure 4: *Experiences that shape pedagogical decisions of SPED teachers on the instructional strategies for transition to employment of students with HI*

From the interview, the recurring experiences that shaped the pedagogical decisions of the SPED teachers in choosing instructional strategies to support the transition to the employment of the students with HI are experiences with the reality of employment. These shared experiences among the SPED teacher participants shaped their pedagogical decisions when selecting instructional strategies for the transition to the employment of students with HI to be closely based on the reality of jobs, particularly for people with HI. The participants specified the importance of enabling the students to recognize employees in the context of the real world, having experienced this themselves.

P1: That is why it is best that I share with them whatever are my experiences about society.

P4: If you are a teacher for those in a transition program, it is helpful that you are honest with them. Not all who get a degree will find employment.

The participants added that their pedagogical decisions focus on selecting instructional strategies that expose students with HI to the reality of employment and transitioning to being employed through seminars, talks, and employment shops.

P1: I try to use seminars, talks, and workshops to teach them, and once they are ready to apply for a job, we conduct employment shops.

They also noted that they frequently incorporate their own experiences with employment, which shaped their pedagogical decisions on the instructional strategies to apply to prepare the students with HI on what to expect as they enter employment. The participants identified that sharing personal experiences have helped the students plan and visualise the process of their transition from the classroom to the workplace.

P1: “[...] so that when they graduate, they will know and are aware. If these things are not taught, they might have a culture shock once outside the real world. That is why I think sharing my experiences as a member of society is essential.

DISCUSSIONS, RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

A repertoire of instructional strategies can be used to help HIs transition to work. For example, visual aids may be in any form with a thorough guidance, provide further clarification on the content they are teaching and help the students easily obtain the information and knowledge being taught to them (Pradina & Hastuti, 2017). Although the usage of visual aids, such as the series of slides for a presentation to be used in discussions, should be partnered with enough guidance to help develop and stimulate the students' cognitive skills (Abdullayeva, 2021). The correct usage of visual aids as an instructional strategy for students with hearing impairment can help increase their motivation and interest, which is important for their development (Baglama et al., 2018). In order for the visual aids to create optimal learning for the students with HI, the teachers should be careful in choosing and using ready-made visual aids on the internet (Allman et al., 2019).

Interview findings also reiterated that vocational training and exposure to different possible workplaces are essential for the transition to the employment of students with hearing impairment (Iftikhar et al., (2022). Immersion is an important factor in the transition to employment for students with hearing impairment as it helps develop the skills the students need for their future employment (Acut, 2021). Providing field trips and exposure to different environments helps increase the student's academic success and develop the skills they need for future opportunities (Ogunwale, 2021).

It was inferred from the participants that the utilisation of different kinds of sign language roots confusion (Mendoza, 2018) towards the implementation of instructions. The move from one type of sign language to another lacks transitional indicators. The majority of the time, participants use the SEE because it employs grammatically correct English for subjects that contain English grammar. (Rendel et.al, 2018). ASL is the most used sign language in their school, even though Filipino Sign Language was mandated to be used in the Philippines according to Republic Act 11106 (2018). Although some participants also noted the use of FSL as the mode of communication in a general setting (e.g., break time, recess, outside the school).

The participants consider a post-test of practical writing, which has been used to help students learn more effectively (Alam, 2019), and this learning will subsequently be ingrained in their supplemental knowledge when they write documents. However, there is no default corpora or exact written text of sign American language, which poses difficulty for the participants and their students (Quer & Steinbach, 2019).

Identifying how teachers gather and gain experience to mold the students' transition to employment was determined to be influenced from the inside and outside of school. Education and community involvement are essential for individuals with HI (Kini & Podolsky, n.d), and NGOs have modified service delivery to include deaf or hard-of-hearing teachers (UNESCO, 2020). Studying abroad has provided teachers with experience and information to help them teach students with HI with effective instructional strategies (Misco & Shiveley, 2015). According to Cablao et al. (2020), Investing time and resources is necessary for teacher training. Institutions should support teacher training; however, some make significant investments in the further education of teachers (Rabara, 2017). Another factor identified with the SPED Teachers' influence on experience is that the communication between teachers and parents is integral to supporting the student's decision-making process (Mati et al., 2016). Persistent parental involvement and enhanced language development are critical to the focus of schools, and parent-child connections help learners feel connected, improving the environment for personal and academic achievement in assisting and developing students with HI's social and emotional well-being (Sethi & Scales, 2020; Lennox & Shields, 2017). The primary emphasis of the transition phase in tertiary programs is inadequate for people who are deaf or hard of hearing (Magano & Mapepa, 2018). This harms their psychological domain, potentially increasing their defenselessness to environmental concerns (Sintos, 2020). SPED teachers take measures to secure the good qualities of students with HI in employment to be competent in completing their duties.

Based on the collected data from the participants, the SPED teachers from a postsecondary institution in Makati, Philippines, the teaching experiences that shaped their pedagogical decisions regarding the instructional strategies to employ in support of the transition to the employment of students with HI are experiences with the reality of employment. From the interview, they identified their experiences with employment in the real world to have influenced their pedagogical decisions in such a manner that they apply instructional strategies that would expose students with HI to the real world and simultaneously prepare them for the reality of employment as they inevitably transition from school to work. This coincides with Stein et al.'s (n.d.) study, which claims that teachers' authentic experiences often shape their pedagogical decisions on instruction. Furthermore, Iucu and Marin (2014) support using teachers' authentic experiences to design instruction replicating real-world incidents as nearly as possible. For students with disabilities, including students with HI, building on their authentic learning experiences is significant. It has value beyond school, which makes it imperative for teachers to incorporate real-life elements and authentic learning experiences in their instruction using instructional strategies that reflect this need of the learners (Israel et al., 2013; Herrington et al., 2014; Moore, 2014). In the case of the participants, their authentic experiences with the reality of employment prompted them to use instructional strategies that prepare students with HI for employment in the real world, such as seminars and workshops.

Conclusions

It was ascertained by the research design and gathered data from the participants that the instructional strategies the teachers use to transition to the employment of the students with hearing impairment include visual aids and immersions. The aforementioned instructional strategies gear the students towards employment as these strategies complement and cater to the needs and abilities of the students with hearing impairment to develop the skills they need in various workplaces. The usage of visual aids as an instructional strategy is also a vital factor for the development of the students as it creates an optimal learning environment for the students, but only if the teachers are careful in choosing and using those ready-made visual aids on the internet. Immersion is also deemed an effective instructional strategy for the transition to the employment of the students with hearing impairment as it helps them develop the different needed skills. The usage of sign language as a supporting strategy should also be carefully chosen because using other sign languages to teach students can lead to confusion. The transition to the employment of students with HI necessitates the development of the essential skills needed for employment. SPED teachers help the students develop these skills by utilizing instructional strategies that cater to their interests and abilities and using their experiences to help them decide on what instructional strategies can be efficient to supplement the needs of their students. These results should be interpreted with a limitation, such as having a small sample size, as this study only covered a small-scaled populated postsecondary school in the Philippines. A larger population could gather more instructional strategies to gear the students toward their employment.

Recommendations

For SPED Teachers teaching students with hearing impairment, they should be mindful of their students' characteristics and learning styles to provide the necessary and efficient strategies to develop their needed skills. They can develop enhancement of the instructional approaches teachers employ to teach students with HI; teachers should perpetually collaborate with their co-teacher and other school personnel; Teachers should also undergo additional pieces of training for the betterment of their creation of visual aids to prevent using ready-made materials from the internet.

The study only covers a small-scale population of a postsecondary school in the Philippines. For School Administrators, recommendations are as follows. School administrators should provide them with a learning environment that could further help them transition to employment and associate companies depending on the courses they offer. School administrators may consider providing their teachers with enough instructional strategies to utilize for their students.

Education agencies should also participate in the collaborative efforts of SPED Teachers and School Administration. Educational agencies, specifically DepED and CHED, should ensure the implementation of laws and policies relating to SPED students and persons with HI and provide enough funding for the students' immersions. In terms of employment, DepEd and CHED should reinforce the implementation of the Magna Carta for Disabled Persons in terms of equal opportunity for employment.

Given that the study has limitations, future research can help the topic of instructional strategies for transition to the employment of students with HI become more comprehensive. Future researchers may use a mixed-method approach for their research method to deeper analyze the other strategies used for the students, the perceptions of the teachers before and after utilizing the strategies, and the opinions of the students on the instructional strategies used by them. Future researchers may also conduct a secondary research method to make use of the data gathered in this study to see the effectiveness of the instructional strategies the participants used for the transition to the employment of the students with HI.

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